

Supporting Information

A Flexible Theory for Catalysis: Learning Alkaline Oxygen Reduction on Complex Solid Solutions within the Ag–Pd–Pt–Ru Composition Space

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Measurement of the chemical composition of the materials libraries

The chemical composition of the materials libraries was measured by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) with an acceleration voltage of 20 kV. On each materials library, 81 measurements were done on a regular grid of 9x9 (8.5 mm spacing, cross markers in figure S1, S2, and S3). After the measurement, 2 measurements were removed because the coordinates were outside of the materials library. Linear regression was used to interpolate the composition distribution of the elements over the 342 measurement areas of the 4.5 mm grid that was used in the scanning droplet cell experiments (round markers in figure S1, S2, and S3). Linear regression was fitted for each element individually, taking the x and y coordinate as input to predict the element abundance for each measurement area. After fitting, the element abundance was predicted for all 342 measurement coordinates of the SDC measurements. After linear regression, the chemical composition of each measurement area is calculated in atomic % (at.%). The mean absolute error of the interpolation was 1.5 to 2.5 at.%.

Figure S1 Chemical composition of the materials libraries Ag-Pd-Ru (top row) and Ag-Pd-Pt (bottom row) plotted over the measurement areas. Round points are measurement areas of the SDC experiments. Crosses are measurement areas for EDX. Points are coloured according to the atomic percent (at.%) of the given element as shown by the corresponding colorbar.

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Figure S2 Chemical composition of the materials libraries Pd-Pt-Ru (top row) and Ag-Pt-Ru (bottom row) plotted over the measurement areas. Round points are measurement areas of the SDC experiments. Crosses are measurement areas for EDX. Points are coloured according to the atomic percent (at.%) of the given element as shown by the corresponding colorbar.

Figure S3 Chemical composition of the materials library Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru plotted over the measurement areas. Round points are measurement areas of the SDC experiments. Crosses are measurement areas for EDX. Points are coloured according to the atomic percent (at.%) of the given element as shown by the corresponding colorbar.

Figure S4 Annotated photo of the Scanning Droplet Cell (SDC) setup

Electrochemical measurements of linear sweep voltammograms

All electrochemical measurements were conducted with the use of a high-throughput scanning droplet cell (SDC), which allows localized characterization of selected compositions along the compositional gradient. SDC head incorporates counter (Pt wire) and reference (Ag|AgCl|3M KCl) electrodes and a Teflon tip with ca. 1mm diameter opening which forms a working electrode on the surface of the investigated sample in every spot where the tip touches the sample. Precise positioning and pressing the tip to the investigated sample is enabled by assembling the SDC head with robotic arms and a force sensor. The electrolyte is replaced with a fresh portion for every measuring area. The automated setup maintains identical measurement conditions, thus the electrocatalytic activity can be compared between the measuring areas and material libraries. The surface area of the tip opening was used as a geometrical area of the working electrode for the calculation of measured current densities. All linear sweep voltammograms were measured in 0.05 M KOH, pH12.5, with a scan rate of 10 mV/s.

All potentials are reported versus the RHE according to the following equation:

$$U_{\text{RHE}} \text{ (V)} = U_{(\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}|\text{3 M KCl})} + 0.210 + (0.059 \text{ pH}),$$

where $U_{(\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}|\text{3 M KCl})}$ is the potential measured versus Ag|AgCl|3 M KCl reference electrode, 0.210 V is the standard potential of the Ag|AgCl|3 M KCl reference electrode at 25 °C. Note that 0.059 is the result of $(RT) \cdot (nF)^{-1}$, where R is the gas constant, T is the temperature (298 K), F is the Faraday constant, and n is the number of electrons transferred during the reaction.

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Figure S5 LSVs from the five material libraries included in the study after exclusion of noisy measurements and adjustment of the Ag-Pt-Ru measurements as described in the main text and shown in figure S5. Each sweep is colored according to the fraction of Ag (capped at 75%) in the as-deposited bulk composition of the measurement area on the library from where the sweep was collected. A three-dimensional simplex of the Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru composition space with all sampled points is included.

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Figure S6 LSVs from the five material libraries included in the study after exclusion of noisy measurements and adjustment of the Ag-Pt-Ru measurements as described in the main text and shown in figure S5. Each sweep is colored according to the fraction of Pd (capped at 75%) in the as-deposited bulk composition of the measurement area on the library from where the sweep was collected. A three-dimensional simplex of the Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru composition space with all sampled points is included.

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Figure S7 LSVs from the five material libraries included in the study after exclusion of noisy measurements and adjustment of the Ag-Pt-Ru measurements as described in the main text and shown in figure S5. Each sweep is colored according to the fraction of Pt (capped at 75%) in the as-deposited bulk composition of the measurement area on the library from where the sweep was collected. A three-dimensional simplex of the Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru composition space with all sampled points is included.

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Figure S8 LSVs from the five material libraries included in the study after exclusion of noisy measurements and adjustment of the Ag-Pt-Ru measurements as described in the main text and shown in figure S5. Each sweep is colored according to the fraction of Ru (capped at 75%) in the as-deposited bulk composition of the measurement area on the library from where the sweep was collected. A three-dimensional simplex of the Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru composition space with all sampled points is included.

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Figure S9 a) 8 pairs of LSVs from the Ag-Pt-Ru and Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru libraries colored red and blue, respectively. The as-deposited alloy compositions of the measurement areas differ by less than 2%. As such, the LSVs should be nearly identical; however, there is a visible offset between the measurements. b) The resulting LSVs after applying a correction to the Ag-Pt-Ru library to minimize the difference in measured current density at 850 mV vs. RHE. c) A three-dimensional simplex of the Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru composition space showing the alloy compositions of the LSVs

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Details on density functional theory calculations and GNN training

The DFT calculations used to train the GNN for adsorption energy inference used the revised Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (RPBE) exchange-correlation functional^[48] implemented in the GPAW code^[49,50]. All surfaces were modeled with ASE^[51] as 3x3x5 atom-sized fcc(111) slabs with lateral periodic boundary conditions and a vacuum of 10.0 Å added above and below the slab. The only exception to this were some datasets on binary alloys that were modeled as 3x4x5 atom-sized with a vacuum of 7.5 Å. The lattice constant of each structure was set to the weighted average of the calculated fcc lattice constants of the elements in the surface layer to avoid imposing unwanted lattice strain^[52]. The atoms in the two bottom layers were held fixed and the structures were optimized until the maximum force on any atom was below at least 0.1 eV/Å. The wave functions were expanded in plane waves with an energy cutoff set to 400 eV, and the Brillouin zone was sampled with a Monkhorst-Pack grid^[53] of 4x4x1 k-points. Pt(111) references were made for both slab sizes and used to calculate the adsorption energy as:

$$\Delta G_{*ads}^{DFT} = \Delta E_{slab+ads}^{DFT} - \Delta E_{slab}^{DFT} - \Delta E_{Pt(111)+ads}^{DFT} + \Delta E_{Pt(111)}^{DFT}$$

with $\Delta E_{slab+ads}^{DFT}$ and ΔE_{slab}^{DFT} being the calculated total energy of the slab with and without adsorbate, respectively. $\Delta E_{Pt(111)+ads}^{DFT}$ and $\Delta E_{Pt(111)}^{DFT}$ is the calculated total energy of the Pt(111) reference slab, also with and without adsorbate. OH and O were only placed adsorbed on the ontop and fcc hollow sites, respectively, after relaxation of the bare slab. For some slabs multiple different sites were sampled on the same slab to minimize the number of calculations needed.

Different datasets of DFT calculations listed in Table S1 were used in a 70:15:15 split to form the composite training, validation, and test sets so that all sub-alloys were equally represented in each set. The GNN was set up within the pyTorch^[54] framework, and graph construction, training, and model parameters were identical to the previously published version.

Table S1. Overview of the multiple different data sets of DFT calculations used to train the GNN. The sampling schemes refer to how the atom composition of the slabs were chosen and are as follows: *Uniformly* sampled slabs had sets of probabilities drawn from a Dirichlet distribution with uniform density in the composition space ($\alpha = 1$), and the atom identities of the slab were subsequently determined by that set of probabilities. *Centered* slabs were sampled identically but with $\alpha = 2.5$ to obtain a higher density of compositions from the center of the composition space. *Equimolar* slabs had their atom identities chosen with equal probability. *Mixed* refers to multiple different sampling schemes combined.

Alloy	Number of *OH samples	Number of *O samples	Sampling scheme
Ag-Ir-Pd-Pt-Ru	2519	2520	Uniformly
Ag-Ir-Pd-Pt-Ru	1899	1809	Equimolar
Ag-Ir-Pd-Pt	470	475	Equimolar
Ag-Ir-Pd-Ru	444	426	Equimolar
Ag-Ir-Pt-Ru	455	464	Equimolar
Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru	466	447	Equimolar
Ir-Pd-Pt-Ru	441	482	Equimolar
Ag-Pd-Pt	183	205	Equimolar
Ag-Pd-Ru	400	376	Equimolar
Ir-Pd-Pt	202	204	Equimolar
Pd-Pt-Ru	98	105	Equimolar
Ag-Ir	209	238	Centered
Ag-Pd	764	501	Mixed
Ag-Pd ^a	468	497	Mixed

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Ag-Pt	332	401	Centered
Ag-Ru	307	360	Centered
Ir-Pd	310	308	Centered
Ir-Pd ^a	449	480	Mixed
Ir-Pt	201	201	Centered
Ir-Pt ^a	498	500	Mixed
Ir-Ru	195	200	Centered
Pd-Pt	200	199	Centered
Pd-Ru	192	190	Centered
Pd-Ru ^a	493	481	Mixed
Pt-Ru	196	201	Centered
Pt-Ru ^a	349	489	Mixed
Total	12740	12759	

[a] 3x4x5 atom-sized slabs

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Figure S10 Errors of the trained GNN on the composite AgIrPdPtRu test set. a and b) Parity plots of predicted adsorption energies relative to Pt(111) of *OH and *O , respectively. Histograms show the distribution of errors. c) Boxplots showing the median, first, and third quartiles as well as the 5% and 95% limits of error for each of the alloy subsets of the composite test set.

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Details on fit and prediction of catalytic activities

The adjustable parameters of the theoretical prediction model outlined in equations 1 and 2 were fitted with an L-BFGS-B procedure implemented in Scipy's minimize function. The initial values for a , b , and ΔG_{opt} were set to -1, 0.5, and 0.1, respectively. Similarly, the bounds on the individual parameters were $]-\infty, 0]$, $[0, 1]$, and $[-0.1, 0.3]$. For application of linear regression, Gaussian process regression, gradient boosted decision tree and random forest the implementations in scikit-learn^[65] were utilized. With linear regression, the regression algorithm was constrained to solely negative weights and an intercept of zero when applied to histograms of adsorption energies. The kernel used for Gaussian process regression was:

$$k(x_i, x_j) = c \cdot e^{-\frac{d(x_i, x_j)}{2l^2}} \quad (S1)$$

with $d(x_i, x_j)$ being the Euclidean distance between two feature vectors and l as well as c being adjustable parameters. Gradient boosted decision trees and random forest were applied with their default scikit-learn settings.

The above-mentioned models were either applied to the as-deposited bulk composition represented by a vector containing the element fractions or to a vector containing the bin counts of a histogram of the adsorption energy distribution obtained from a simulated surface with the bulk composition. The bin width was chosen to be 0.1 eV, resulting in 24 bins for *OH and *O energies, respectively.

Table S2. Resulting MAE [mA/cm²] for the cross-validation of different prediction models for current densities as described in the main text. Specific results mentioned in the text have been highlighted in bold.

Prediction model	Input features						
	Bulk composition	Gross ΔG_{OH}	Gross ΔG_O	Gross ΔG_{OH+O}	Net ΔG_{OH}	Net ΔG_O	Net ΔG_{OH+O}
a ^[a]	Not applicable	0.190	0.091	0.074	0.184	0.096	0.145
$a + b$ ^[a]	Not applicable	0.067	0.102	0.042	0.062	0.096	0.058
$a + \Delta G_{opt}$ ^[a]	Not applicable	0.155	0.108	0.069	0.148	0.143	0.111
$a + b + \Delta G_{opt}$ ^[a]	Not applicable	0.083	0.113	0.046	0.066	0.097	0.062
Linear Regression	0.052	0.069	0.075	0.043	0.089	0.079	0.078
Gaussian Process Regression	0.052	0.074	0.076	0.058	0.080	0.066	0.101
Gradient Boosted Decision Tree	0.059	0.078	0.060	0.060	0.078	0.055	0.053
Random Forest	0.065	0.084	0.066	0.060	0.083	0.050	0.060

[a] Theoretical model with fitting of the listed adjustable parameters.

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Figure S11 Parity plots showing predicted current density at 850 mV vs. RHE against experimentally observed current density. Each plot shows a fold in the cross-validation scheme where a single material library was held as a test set and the remaining libraries were used to fit the a and b terms in equations 1 and 2. All alloy compositions are colored according to the fraction of Ag (capped at 75%). The three-dimensional simplexes show the library's position in the Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru composition space.

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Figure S12 Parity plots showing predicted current density at 850 mV vs. RHE against experimentally observed current density. Each plot shows a fold in the cross-validation scheme where a single material library was held as a test set and the remaining libraries were used to fit the a and b terms in equations 1 and 2. All alloy compositions are colored according to the fraction of Pd (capped at 75%). The three-dimensional simplexes show the library's position in the Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru composition space.

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Figure S13 Parity plots showing predicted current density at 850 mV vs. RHE against experimentally observed current density. Each plot shows a fold in the cross-validation scheme where a single material library was held as a test set and the remaining libraries were used to fit the a and b terms in equations 1 and 2. All alloy compositions are colored according to the fraction of Pt (capped at 75%). The three-dimensional simplexes show the library's position in the Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru composition space.

Figure S14 Parity plots showing predicted current density at 850 mV vs. RHE against experimentally observed current density. Each plot shows a fold in the cross-validation scheme where a single material library was held as a test set and the remaining libraries were used to fit a linear regression model on binned adsorption energies. All alloy compositions are colored according to the fraction of Ru (capped at 75%) as illustrated by the colorbar. The three-dimensional simplexes show the library's position in the Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru composition space.

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Figure S15 By taking a test sample's particular bin count of adsorption energies and multiplying them with the bin weight from the multiple linear regression fit, we get the contribution of that particular bin to the predicted current density of the test sample. These are shown here as a violin plot that visualizes the distribution of contributions for each bin in the histogram's adsorption energies. The contributions for each sample were calculated when the sample was held as part of the test set of cross-validation fold.

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Figure S16 Parity plots showing predicted current density at 850 mV vs. RHE against experimentally observed current density. Each plot shows a fold in the cross-validation scheme where a single ternary material library was used as a training set and used to fit the *a* and *b* terms in equations 1 and 2, while the remaining three ternary libraries were held as test sets. All alloy compositions are colored according to the fraction of Ru (capped at 75%). The three-dimensional simplexes show the library's position in the Ag-Pd-Pt-Ru composition space.

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Figure S17 Two-dimensional Ag-Pd-Pt simplexes showing contours of the predicted current density at 850 mV vs. RHE for a selection of models: a) A Gaussian Process Regression model fitted to the bulk compositions of all samples included in this study to show the best possible extrapolation from the performed experiments. b) The standard deviation of the model showing areas of prediction uncertainty. c) Theory-derived model with adjustable parameter a fitted on the net adsorption energy distributions. d) Theory-derived model with adjustable parameters a and b fitted on the gross adsorption energy distributions. For both c) and d), the models were fitted on all samples except the Ag-Pd-Pt library.

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Figure S18 Two-dimensional Ag-Pd-Ru simplexes showing contours of the predicted current density at 850 mV vs. RHE for a selection of models: a) A Gaussian Process Regression model fitted to the bulk compositions of all samples included in this study to show the best possible extrapolation from the performed experiments. b) The standard deviation of the model showing areas of prediction uncertainty. c) Theory-derived model with adjustable parameter a fitted on the net adsorption energy distributions. d) Theory-derived model with adjustable parameters a and b fitted on the gross adsorption energy distributions. For both c) and d), the models were fitted on all samples except the Ag-Pd-Ru library.

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Figure S19 Two-dimensional Ag-Pt-Ru simplexes showing contours of the predicted current density at 850 mV vs. RHE for a selection of models: a) A Gaussian Process Regression model fitted to the bulk compositions of all samples included in this study to show the best possible extrapolation from the performed experiments. b) The standard deviation of the model showing areas of prediction uncertainty. c) Theory-derived model with adjustable parameter a fitted on the net adsorption energy distributions. d) Theory-derived model with adjustable parameters a and b fitted on the gross adsorption energy distributions. For both c) and d), the models were fitted on all samples except the Ag-Pt-Ru library.

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Figure S20 Two-dimensional Pd-Pt-Ru simplexes showing contours of the predicted current density at 850 mV vs. RHE for a selection of models: a) A Gaussian Process Regression model fitted to the bulk compositions of all samples included in this study to show the best possible extrapolation from the performed experiments. b) The standard deviation of the model showing areas of prediction uncertainty. c) Theory-derived model with adjustable parameter a fitted on the net adsorption energy distributions. d) Theory-derived model with adjustable parameters a and b fitted on the gross adsorption energy distributions. For both c) and d), the models were fitted on all samples except the Pd-Pt-Ru library.

Details on adjusting alloy compositions

To get a qualitative estimate of the trend in the discrepancy between the as-deposited bulk composition and the actual surface composition of the measurement areas during reaction conditions, we applied a “wandering compositions” procedure: In the cross-validation of the best performing prediction model (solely fitting parameters a and b of the theory-derived model on the gross adsorption energy distributions), the test samples were subsequently allowed to be altered in a stepwise manner to better fit the predicted current density. This was done iteratively for each sample, whose composition could move on a grid with 1% resolution in steps of up to 5% until no better-fitting predicted current density was within 5%. Figure 4b shows the new compositions of each ternary material library after this procedure.

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